

The impact of internet finance on the service provision of commercial banks

May Yue Zhang^{1*}, Joel G. Matamis²

¹Master of Business Administration Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

²School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: 389882806@qq.com

Abstract

With the reform of the overall financial environment and the promotion of the market system, the development of many banks in China has made great progress and great changes. In recent years, China's commercial banks have experienced a variety of measures, such as joint-stock reform and financial restructuring, and the overall operating pressure has been released accordingly. In the face of increasingly fierce market competition, commercial banks have upgraded their business ideas from a single focus on business scale to a dual focus on business scale and quality. Although we have made great achievements on the road, we cannot ignore the fact that diversified financial risks still exist. Whether from the perspective of practice or academia, the financial risk management of commercial banks has generally received the focus of attention. Based on the cited literature, this paper elaborates on the current situation of the operation and financial risk management of commercial banks in China. Starting from the basic data of many domestic commercial banks, we focused on the analysis of their management status in combination with their business types. We further explored all aspects of the financial risk management of commercial banks by focusing on assets, liabilities, profits and losses, non-performing loans, overdue loans, and banking assessment indicators. We also summarized different evaluation systems and models and analyzed and summarized the advantages and disadvantages of each item.

Keywords: *Commercial bank; Structural system; Financial risk.*

To cite this article:

Zhang, M. Y., & Matamis, J. G. (2021). The impact of internet finance on the service provision of commercial banks. *The Executives*, 2, 107-120.

Introduction

At the beginning of 2015, Premier Li Keqiang came to China's first Internet bank. He personally touched the button to issue the first loan and hoped that the development of Internet finance could force bank reform. In the government work report, Internet finance was also mentioned. The government's attitude towards Internet finance has gradually changed from recognition to encouragement, and the development environment of Internet finance is getting better and better, while the market environment faced by China's commercial banks can only be said to be "besieged on all sides."

The first is the unstoppable process of determining the market interest rate. China's market interest rate reform has been conducted for many years, and now it has entered the stage of marketization of deposit and loan interest rates. The marketization of interest rates not only reduces the financing costs of enterprises but also changes the pattern so that banks can make high profits by stabilizing the deposit loan interest margin. The second is the development of the financial disintermediation trend. On the scale of social financing, the proportion of bank credit is gradually declining. Social financing no longer only depends on banks as intermediaries but gradually constructs a diversified financing system of small loans, private placement, and bonds.

The third is the impact of private capital. China's policy control on the entry of private capital into the financial industry is gradually relaxed, attracting a large number of private capital into the banking industry. While increasing the competitiveness and vitality of the banking industry, it also increases the pressure on the original commercial banks. Lam et al. (2015) conducted questionnaires on some customers in 2007, 2011, and 2014. The survey results show that the proportion of customers in the top four banks is gradually decreasing, from 79 percentage points in 2007 to 73 percentage points in 2014, while the competitiveness of joint-stock banks is improving, from 6 percentage points in 2007 to 16 percentage points in 2014.

Internet finance has attracted more attention in recent years. Since 2018, the Internet has gradually expanded into the financial industry based on its own platform and data. Third-party payment, online financing, crowdfunding, peer-to-peer (P2P) service, and other Internet financial models have become an indispensable part of the online lives of many netizens (Zhang, 2020). Its vigorous development prompted the reform of commercial banks. In the face of the expansion of Internet finance, it will be the focus of each commercial bank to protect its territory from invasion.

In the new economy formed by the impact of the Internet, users' consumption habits, including financial habits, have undergone tremendous changes. More than half of online transactions occur during non-working hours. Under the dual restrictions of time and place, traditional commercial banks have become increasingly unable to meet users' needs for efficiency and convenience, and the transformation of commercial banks is imminent. Only by embracing the Internet spirit with a more open attitude, continuously expanding the service model of banks, and gradually innovating on the basis of expansion so that ordinary people can become beneficiaries of inclusive finance can commercial banks achieve considerable development in this important opportunity period. Therefore, the research on the transformation of commercial banks is of great significance and can provide certain reference values for the innovation and transformation of commercial banks.

O'Reilly (2015) said that statistics by Goldman Sachs show that, globally, the percentage of all payments made using mobile terminals in 2011 was 1.0%, and by 2015, the proportion will reach 2.2%. The mobile phone client has been able to provide customers with stock trading, payment, and other services and may also provide credit card services in the future. Mishkin (2018) explained that the first reason financial media exists is that it can generate economies of scale and has a professional team to provide professional services, which can reduce transaction costs. The second is that it has the ability to store, transform, and use information and can use this ability to reduce the information asymmetry between the deposit and loan sides, thereby reducing risks. Scott (2000) conducted a lot of research on information on social networks, believing that they can gather a lot of information and provide rich data. For example, in the process of user contact and communication, a large amount of information will be generated. Shirky (2009) studied the development of the Internet and various communication facilities and believed that in the process of this development, people have reduced the cost of communication and liaison and even created a completely different division of labor model, such as human flesh search.

The Impact of Internet Finance on Banks

Cao (2013) analyzed the advantages and disadvantages of commercial banks and concluded that Internet finance provides them with development impetus, which is an opportunity to promote the reform and development of banks. Wang (2014) believed that the development of Internet finance had a huge impact on commercial banks and changed the business pattern of banks. Xu (2014) believed that, compared with the banking industry, Internet finance has improved financing efficiency, but there are also some operational and technical risks. Wang (2015) used the Delphi method and the analytic hierarchy process to analyze the impact of Internet finance on banks.

Qiu (2018) concluded that the financial intermediary role of commercial banks is being weakened in the analysis of the impact of Internet financial development on commercial banks, and only by strengthening cooperation is the guarantee of their common development. Yuan et al. (2018) believed that banks must innovate service methods and channels to meet challenges. Zhu (2014) used SWOT analysis method to provide some strategies for ICBC to deal with Internet finance. Li (2014) proposed that banks should pay more attention to Internet finance, an emerging financial force, and increase efforts to innovate their online businesses. Lin (2018) believed that facing the development of Internet finance, commercial banks should innovate their development models and create new products to meet challenges and opportunities. Wu (2014) analyzed the advantages of Internet finance from different perspectives such as finance and management. Commercial banks should give up some short-term behaviors and stick to more long-term coping strategies.

The rise of Internet finance has had an important impact on the development of the financial industry and has had a huge impact on the current service system of commercial banks. The relationship between third-party payment institutions and banks was not only strategic cooperation but also confrontation with competition. The big data application and long-tail positioning of Internet finance made financial services more efficient, more convenient, and lower operating costs. These are serious challenges to the business model and customer service of commercial banks.

The strong impact of Internet finance on commercial banks has promoted the process of commercial banks transforming their operations and improving their services. The organic combination of Internet finance and supply chain finance provides a way out of domestic SMEs' financing problems. Commercial banks must actively conduct innovative services and vigorously develop the construction of supply chain financing platforms to meet the challenges of Internet finance. However, the platform still faces many problems, such as low visibility, insufficient external publicity, few online products, little choice for customers, a weak data analysis system, and an imperfect platform management system. The platform construction has a long way to go.

Xie and Zou (2017) analyzed the operation modes of different Internet financial models. Zhang (2013) studied the development, mode, and problems of P2P credit in China and proposed policy suggestions such as strengthening supervision and formulating unified standards. Sun (2013), based on the research on the characteristics and development motivation of various models of Internet finance, believes that it can reduce information asymmetry and transaction costs and that supervision is an important variable affecting the development of Internet finance. Xie et al. (2015) believed that it was necessary to supervise Internet finance, promote development through supervision, and promote innovation under supervision. Zhang (2014), by studying foreign development experience, believed that we should adhere to the twelve principles to supervise the Internet financial industry. Wang and Zhang (2014) believed that Internet finance was the product of the development of Internet technology, and its advantages and disadvantages should be viewed dialectically, and risk control should be strengthened on the basis of rational utilization.

The Impact of Internet Finance on Traditional Commercial Bank Services

Characteristics of traditional commercial bank services

Traditional commercial banks provide financial services to customers by establishing physical outlets and providing face-to-face services through counters. The necessity of this service mode is that some businesses can only be managed in the form of counter services, such as some businesses that need to verify the authenticity of customers' identities, similar to the opening of debit cards (including self-service card collection) and the opening and cancellation of some businesses; or, for example, cash transactions are required for deposit and withdrawal. In addition, counter service also creates conditions for face-to-face customer exchange and communication, realizing further understanding of your customer needs and further creating marketing opportunities. As a traditional service channel, counter service has obvious advantages,

but it also faces problems and challenges. First, the cost of physical outlet counter service is high. The construction of physical outlets requires a large number of financial resources, and maintaining the normal operation of physical outlets also requires sufficient material and human costs. Secondly, the financial service industry is a high-risk industry, and physical outlets require strong protection of property and capital security. In recent years, the number of violent bank robberies has gradually increased, which also puts forward higher requirements for the personal security of bank employees and customers. Thirdly, with the development of Internet technology and the popularization of e-banking businesses in recent years, users' use of bank outlet counter services has decreased significantly, while the proportion of people using electronic channels to manage business has increased year by year. According to the evaluation results, the utilization rate of traditional channels of banks in 2015 decreased significantly compared with that in 2014, and the utilization rate of counters and automated teller machines (ATMs) in physical outlets of banks decreased by more than 10%.

Customer's satisfaction with the bank hall service decreases

The utilization rate of traditional channels dominated by counter services is affected by Internet finance and is gradually declining. At the same time, customers' satisfaction with the service at the outlets is also declining. According to the relevant survey data, nearly 12.27% of bank customers have complained about the bank in the past year. The leading causes of complaints are unreasonable distribution of bank outlets, few service windows, low service efficiency, slow handling speed, and poor attitude of bank tellers. In addition, according to the survey data of the China Quality News Network on customer satisfaction in the banking industry in 2015, the complaint rate of banking customers has reached 29%, and the reasons for complaints are highly concentrated in the service of the business hall. Among them, 48% of customers complain because the business hall has been waiting for a long time to manage business, 16% of customers complain because the service attitude of the staff in the banking hall is poor, 13% of customers are dissatisfied with the slow speed of banking business processing, and 11% of customers complain because of the small number of bank outlets and unreasonable distribution.

Here, taking one of the most prominent problems affecting the satisfaction of banking customers in the banking industry—the long waiting time for customers to manage business in the banking hall—as an example (Zhuo, 2019), according to the data, the average waiting time for customers to handle business in the banking hall in 2015 was more than 20 minutes, accounting for 37%. The reason is that the proportion of manual participation in business processing at outlets is high. Although the uncertainty of business processing time is caused by the uneven quality of bank staff, it should be attributed to the unintelligence of the bank's counter business processing system, the complexity of business processing procedures, and the imperfection of the authorization system to a greater extent, which has caused serious queuing phenomena in the bank and also caused the bad experience of customers. It can be seen that banks need to allocate resources reasonably to ensure service quality.

Internet financial model

Internet financial models mainly include three types: payment and settlement, investment and financing, and financing. The financing mode also includes the P2P online loan platform, crowdfunding mode, Ali financial mode, and supply chain financial mode. As the earliest financial field entered by Internet enterprises, third-party payment is the cornerstone of the development of Internet finance. No matter what kind of Internet mode it is, it needs the support of the payment platform. Payment is the channel for capital recharge and withdrawal and the basis of other Internet financial models. In terms of cost, the third-party payment has concentrated a large number of small amounts of money, which has generated economies of scale and reduced transaction costs. In addition, the operation interface is simple, the process is convenient, the approval is fast, saving customers time, and it is widely welcomed by customers. In the

six years from 2009 to 2014, during the artificial shopping festival of “Double 11”, Alipay's total transaction volume has exploded year by year. While creating the myth of payment transactions every year, it also shows the transaction processing ability of Alipay. In 2014, Alipay had a maximum of 80,000 transactions per second and even more than 2.85 million transactions per minute. These figures are a verification of Alipay’s payment ability and, more importantly, a proof of customers’ trust in online payment.

From the perspective of the development trend of third-party payment in China, it is gradually transferred from offline to online and from online to mobile. At the moment, when physical stores are facing the “closing tide”, many offline stores are gradually seeking cooperation with online payment. Wumart, Wanning, and other offline retailers have won the patronage of many young users by virtue of the “Double Twelfth” effect. Customers can use the Alipay wallet to pay in physical stores and enjoy preferential prices. The convenience of Internet payment has won the return of many young user groups from online to offline for offline merchants. Alipay, Tenpay, and other third-party payments have increased their attention to mobile payments and gradually extended to mobile Internet finance. The transaction volume of Alipay wallet and WeChat payment is gradually increasing, and users are becoming more accustomed to operating transfers through mobile apps. Mobile Internet finance helps people to truly realize payment and financial management anytime, anywhere. In 2017, China’s mobile payment transaction volume was 151.14 billion yuan. By 2018, it had increased by more than seven times, reaching 1,279.74 billion yuan, accounting for nearly a quarter of third-party payment transactions. On the “Double 11” day in 2014 alone, Alipay’s mobile transaction volume exceeded 24 billion yuan, 3.54 times higher than that in 2018, and nearly half of the total transaction volume in 2014. The transaction volume reached 197 million, 4.36 times that of last year.

Investment and wealth management

Internet finance has met the strong investment demand of investors. Traditional finance cannot provide diversified investment channels for ordinary investment clients, and most people’s idle funds can only be stored in banks. However, the emergence of Internet finance has broadened the investment and financing channels of the general public. The convenient, fast, and low access threshold has brought low-asset customers opportunities to enjoy financial services and has rapidly accumulated a large number of popularity for the development of Internet finance.

In the investment and wealth management business, one is to simply use the Internet as a channel and a sales platform to release product information for insurance, funds, and securities and undertake the consignment business. In this regard, securities companies are the first to conduct Internet financial business and have even developed the Internet into the main channel for customers to obtain information and trade securities. Some securities companies have built or cooperated with Internet companies to develop online shopping malls to sell and promote financial products. For example, Guotai Jun’an Securities has set up an Internet Finance Department dedicated to building a dedicated online sales and investment advisory platform for wealth management products. In addition, the insurance industry is gradually changing its marketing mode to “electric shock.” For example, Zhong An Online mainly sells insurance and claims through Internet channels. There are no physical branches, and all businesses are managed online. Relying on the strong sales and claims teams of traditional insurance companies and the advantages of the large number of customer resources of Internet companies, it has completely broken through the original marketing model of the insurance industry.

The other is to combine the existing financial products with the characteristics of the Internet to develop new investment and financial products that meet the needs of the Internet public, such as Yu’e Bao. It is a platform for the online purchase of monetary funds, which will automatically purchase monetary funds for customers. From one yuan, you can buy at any time and redeem at any time, which does not affect customers’ use of the fund for purchase payment or transfer, and users can intuitively see the daily income and fully enjoy the joy of financial management. It has successfully met the needs of customers and

provided opportunities for customers with no financial experience and less capital to enter the financial field. However, Yu'e Bao did not innovate traditional financial business in a complete sense but only combined the original customer resources of the Internet to broaden the sales channels of financial business and use the Internet to serve offline economic activities. It attracts customers to transfer the remaining funds in Alipay into the account of Yu'e Bao, deposit a large amount of accumulated funds in the form of agreement funds, and negotiate with relevant banks through the fund company to improve the bargaining power so as to obtain a higher deposit yield. Now, due to being included in the formal regulatory system, the annual yield of Yu'e Bao has become routine, but its advantages of convenient operation and low threshold still exist, and it can still attract many customers. In addition, there is also the WeChat financial management service jointly developed by Tencent and Huaxia Fund, which uses the social function of WeChat to increase the spread of financial management tools and the convenience of mobile terminals to increase the exposure of financial management tools. 400 million WeChat users can pick up their mobile phones and enjoy convenient and fast fund purchases, cash deposits and withdrawals, and other businesses at home.

The original meaning of P2P is the peer-to-peer interaction between different computers in the local area network. Now it has been extended to a financial term, referring to the process in which the supply and demand parties of funds directly borrow money based on a certain network platform. In essence, P2P belongs to private microlending, which is a mode of gathering small amounts of funds to lend to people in need of funds. It can bring convenience and cost reduction to both lenders and borrowers and is popular with both investors and financiers. At the same time, the strong financing demand of small and medium-sized enterprises has also catalyzed the development of P2P. In recent years, the number of network platforms in China has increased dramatically. Since 2010, the average annual growth rate of the number of network operation platforms has reached 274%. The development prospects of P2P lending platforms are also optimistic for the market. In 2014, the outstanding amount of its borrowers reached more than 100 billion yuan, nearly four times the amount in 2018. The number of investors reached more than one million, 4.64 times that of last year. The number of borrowers reached 630,000, a year-on-year increase of 3.20 times.

The supply chain finance model is a financing model based on the full integration of all resources in the industrial chain. In the supply chain, information flow, capital flow, and logistics are gathered, and there is a huge demand for financing. As a member of the supply chain, the financier has a more detailed understanding of the overall operation of the industrial chain and risk prevention, which is conducive to reducing financing risks. In addition, based on the big data information records and data models provided by Internet finance, we can evaluate the default rate and other related indicators and give credit ratings to achieve risk assessment, reduce the risk of being defrauded, and reduce the non-performing loan rate.

JD Mall is a typical representative of Internet enterprises providing such services to customers. It does not directly provide loans to customers but cooperates with financial institutions. Jingdong Mall provides financial institutions with technical services and financing information reference based on long-term accumulated data and information from upstream and downstream of the supply chain and does not directly bear financing risks or risk prevention. Merchant customers who need supply chain financial services can use the credit and scale of JD Mall as guarantees to apply for small short-term loans in financial institutions without using physical objects or assets as collateral. Realize the seamless connection between Internet enterprises and financial institutions and jointly build a supply chain financial service platform for e-commerce platform customers.

Internet finance has four obvious advantages over traditional financial models:

First, it can better meet customer needs and provide a wider range of services. Whether payment type, financing type, or monetary fund financing type, they are all based on the needs of customers, supplemented by a large amount of credit and capital data accumulated on the Internet platform for a long time, and can provide services for customers at any time. No matter at any time or place, customers can

handle business as long as they need and do not have to wait in line, which greatly reduces the time cost for customers. In addition, customers do not need to provide various mortgages and guarantees, nor do they need to spend a lot of time and energy waiting for the audit, so they can enjoy the convenient services brought by Internet finance.

Second, the operation cost is low, and the customer base is large. Internet finance mainly relies on Internet technology to reduce labor and operating costs, which can be as low as 1/16 of the cost of physical institutions. Internet finance can expand its service field to tens of millions of SMEs or individual customers, further reducing service costs in economies of scale. In addition, Internet finance better served “small customers” who could not be served due to the limited material resources and manpower of banks and could not provide accurate credit by online and offline credit surveys, e-commerce business ratings, and other methods.

Third, the information integration processing capability is stronger, and the credit evaluation method is more scientific. Internet finance bypasses the credit evaluation method of traditional finance and instead uses data such as operation traces and sales performance left by customers on the network for analysis. The goals are to generate, disseminate, and collect information on social networks and search engines; use big data to comprehensively collect and analyze information related to the subject to build an evaluation system for the subject’s credit; model and analyze information with cloud computing; and improve the integrity and accuracy of information on the basis of reducing information processing costs. Based on this information, the customer’s financial status can be grasped in real time, and the credit rating can be reasonably assessed. These records are naturally generated in the customer’s operation or social networking process, which saves the process and cost of collecting information specifically for customer credit rating and also avoids the customer's fraud in applying for loans and unnecessary losses.

Fourth, the customer experience was better, and customer stickiness increased. With channels and information, Internet finance can provide customers with more accurate services and improve customer recognition. In addition, compared with the traditional financial industry, it has better operation convenience and interactivity. The supply and demand parties can quickly find each other’s needs and conduct transactions. While reducing the transaction links, each customer can reasonably express their opinions on the product to promote the improvement of the product, which greatly improves the customer’s sense of participation and customer stickiness.

Impact of Internet on Financial Industry

Ma Yun said, “*The financial industry needs troublemakers.*” Internet enterprises really stirred up the whole situation in the process of entering the financial field. The application of cloud computing, big data, and other Internet technologies to the financial industry has greatly improved the speed and efficiency of information transmission, reduced the cost of information processing, and further promoted the development of the financial industry based on information processing. In addition, the concept of freedom, openness, and convenience contained in the Internet itself has also impacted the closeness and conservatism of the traditional financial industry. What the Internet brings to finance is not only the innovation of products but also the transformation and production of operating mechanisms and culture in the industry. The Internet provides a more diversified channel for both sides of financing and reduces the asymmetry of information to a certain extent. Based on this, Internet finance has had a huge impact on the business situation of commercial banks.

Service concept: customer-oriented, focusing on the customer experience. The customer experience is the cornerstone of the development and survival of Internet platforms. No matter what kind of Internet enterprise they are, they are very concerned about the customer experience. Internet finance is more customer-oriented, based on the actual needs of customers, to explore potential markets in order to attract appropriate customers to enjoy appropriate products and services and increase customer stickiness. The

traditional service of commercial banks is to sell products to customers based on their own interests. Customers have few options and can only choose the most suitable products passively. For example, in the insurance business of traditional finance, insurance brokers or agents only constantly promote customers to achieve results, while customers find it difficult to find products that are completely suitable for them, with a poor sense of experience. Ali Finance has indicated that it will cooperate with qualified insurance companies to develop more insurance products and services to meet the needs of different customers.

Service mode: transform into Internet operations and weaken financial intermediaries. Internet finance expands financial business to the network, gradually weakening the role of commercial banks as financial intermediaries. From the perspective of payment business, the third-party payment platform can provide customers with payment, transfer, and other businesses, replacing the relevant payment functions of banks; from the perspective of financial management business, various monetary funds have attracted a large number of bank deposits due to their low purchase threshold, convenient redemption, convenient operation, and high income; and from the perspective of financing business, the fund supply and demand parties directly seek business partners by using the platform, bypassing the bank as an intermediary and directly affecting the bank's deposit and loan business. The traditional business mode of the bank is the standardized process of operation on the counter. Although with the progress of technology, network banking, telephone banking, and other service channels have been gradually introduced, only traditional services are copied to new channels, and to some extent, innovation still cannot be reflected, and the service mode has not been fundamentally changed.

Service object: attach importance to the value of SMEs and pay attention to long-tail customers. The traditional commercial credit model is unable to accurately rate customers below a certain standard, which leads to the inability of commercial banks to provide better services for some small customers. Internet finance has built a comprehensive online and offline rating system, creating opportunities for small customers to participate in finance. For example, Alibaba Finance integrates the customer information of the buyer and the seller accumulated on its platform, introduces the network data model, and evaluates all records to help Alibaba better identify the normal financing needs of small businesses and customers with solvency and avoid risks, thus promoting Alibaba Finance to provide qualified small and medium-sized enterprise customers with microloans.

Limitations of Internet Finance

As a new thing, Internet finance has some advantages that commercial banks cannot match, but it also has some limitations. Among them, the most prominent is the potential risk. In the financial field, risk control is very important. However, due to the openness and high transparency of Internet finance itself, although it can reduce the asymmetry of information, it is also easy to disclose customers' privacy. In addition, the technical level needs to be improved, which has certain risks for customers' information and capital security and identification. In addition, due to the rapid development of Internet finance and the lack of a corresponding legal supervision system, existing Internet enterprises have entered the legal gray zone, and some have even touched the legal bottom line. For example, the illegal deposit of Dongfang Venture Capital has sounded the alarm for other similar platforms.

The second is regulatory risk. Payments and transactions in Internet finance are conducted online. The virtualization of the transaction process and the fuzziness of the transaction object may cause various risks in the process, increasing the difficulty and complexity of supervision by the regulatory authority. In addition, it is difficult for regulators to take corresponding measures against specific financial risks because they cannot fully grasp the information of the regulated. The increased difficulty of supervision further increases the risk of platform transactions.

The third is the associated risk. In Internet finance, the possibility of various financial products triggering the outbreak of associated financial risks increases. Due to the innovation of a variety of financial

products and the enhancement of relevance, as well as the participation of many banks, the boundaries between financial institutions and financial businesses are more blurred, and the relevance of risk is stronger. The involvement of the Internet may lead to a large-scale financial crisis. Fourth is the liquidity risk. The vouchers among the major platforms involved in Internet finance cannot be circulated, reducing the liquidity of vouchers. Once the platform goes bankrupt or other problems occur, the vouchers cannot be realized, which will cause losses to investors and lead to a loss of capital for investors.

The fifth is operational risk. As Internet finance is still a new type of service, there may be operational errors in the industry, such as imperfect processes, unfamiliar businesses, and non-standard operations, which may lead to operational risks. When these risk problems involve the vital interests of consumers or users, they can be reflected in two aspects: the customer's capital security and information security. In terms of funds, customers whose funds are stored on the platform, especially those with poor operational efficiency, are likely to suffer from the risk of platform collapse, runaway, or operational errors at any time. In addition, the openness of the network and the imperfection of encryption technology are also very likely to cause customers' financial losses when viruses or hackers attack them. In terms of information, as transaction information is transmitted via the Internet, it is very easy to be leaked or stolen illegally in the process, resulting in frequent network information security incidents. For example, in 2017, more than 80% or 456 million people encountered such problems.

Innovation of Commercial Bank Service Mode

With the vigorous development of Internet finance, the convenient and flexible service mode has attracted many users and shared the market share of banks. In the face of the strong expansion of Internet finance, commercial banks actively conduct self-reform and, on the basis of consolidating the existing service model, continue to extend to the field of Internet finance, integrating the advantages of Internet finance. Taking this opportunity, this paper has designed an innovative structure for a commercial bank service model. Based on the extension to Internet finance, commercial banks must pay more attention to service mode, service object, and service content in the process of renovating service mode.

The inevitable trend of commercial bank service model innovation

Faced with the continuous expansion of Internet finance, commercial banks can only attract more customer groups by constantly innovating their service models and maintaining and expanding the influence of commercial banks on the basis of their original customers. Only innovation can drive commercial banks to keep up with the development, and the innovation of service modes is the way of self-reform. The inevitability of banking service model innovation comes from two aspects: one is internal factors, and the other is the external environment.

After years of development, the banking industry lacks differentiation in competition. By the end of 2014, there were more than 4,000 banking institutions, but their products, services, and market positioning tended to be the same. Most banks only take the difference between deposits and loans as their profit point, and their products lack innovation. To win in the service market, differentiation is a very important development trend. With the development of the financial industry, customers have become more proficient in financial knowledge, and correspondingly, they have more and more rich demand for financial services provided by banks. Only by providing different featured products for different market groups can we meet the needs of customers to the greatest extent. Therefore, banks can increase the innovation of service models, increase the research and development of new products, turn the profit point to the income of bank service fees, broaden the income channels of banks, and improve the competitiveness of banks. The innovation of the service mode of commercial banks can bring more active innovation factors to banks, stimulate the innovation vitality of banks, and develop more differentiated products for market demand.

External environment

This year's government work report proposed "Internet Plus", showing the government's support for the integration of the Internet into traditional industries. The Internet, due to its openness and convenience, has rapidly expanded to many industries, causing many industries to reshuffle. It has brought changes to many traditional industries, not only in the field of technology but also in ideology, systems, laws, and regulations. This includes the subversion of e-commerce platforms such as Taobao and Jingdong Mall to the retail industry; the disruption of WeChat and microblog social networking platforms to the communication industry; and the invasion of many group buying websites in the catering industry and the tourism industry.

The integration of the Internet and many industries has formed a distinctive Internet economy, which naturally requires different financial support. The development of the Internet convergence industry and the growth of its demand for payment have gradually generated a huge demand for Internet finance. The government report in 2015 also proposed to promote mass entrepreneurship so as to drive the rapid development of China's economy. Mass entrepreneurship and innovation cannot be separated from financial support, especially Internet finance, which can provide more abundant products for grassroots people and small and micro enterprises.

The government's strong support for "Internet plus" and innovation and entrepreneurship has become a catalyst for the continuous development of Internet finance. Under the strong impact of Internet finance, the development of commercial banks can no longer confine their vision to their own sphere of influence but should follow the pace of the times to seek self-reform to adapt to the changing external environment.

Expansion of commercial bank service model

The expansion of the service model of commercial banks should be customer-demand-oriented. On the basis of meeting customer needs, consolidate the existing model that can provide customers with safe services, develop the Internet financial model that can provide customers with convenient services, and innovate a new service model that integrates the advantages of both sides.

The first is to consolidate the existing service model. The existing service model of commercial banks is formed by continuously accumulating experience and improving processes in the process of serving customers, and it has advantages that many Internet financial enterprises cannot achieve in a short time. In our future work, we should consolidate the existing advantages of the bank. Not only the development of Internet finance but also the construction of physical outlets. Physical outlets have a higher grasp of risk control and are more suitable for serving high-net-worth customers with huge wealth value, which is irreplaceable. In the future, we can adopt the dual-track model of standardized products serving the public and customized expert services for high-end markets.

Secondly, we should also establish a sense of service that focuses on customer needs. It can better meet the bank's customer needs, constantly improve service quality, provide close service, and attract and retain customers. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen the professional skills training of personnel, improve the professional service quality of employees, promote employees to be more professional, bring customers higher-quality services, and strive to do everything around customer needs.

Thirdly, we should expand the whole service process. We should not only attach importance to the services provided to customers in the process of handling business in the branch during business hours, but also attach importance to the convenience of services provided during non-business hours, the maintenance of equipment operations, and the services that can timely and accurately respond to customers' inquiries. We should rely on the bank's own hardware equipment, turn intangible services into tangible services, and

let customers feel the irreplaceable nature of banking services with an elegant environment, a harmonious atmosphere, smooth processes, and convenient services. Also, we should consolidate and utilize the existing experience, trust mechanism, and proximity advantages; constantly develop and improve; give play to the bank's unique value and role; and convey modern service characteristics and service concepts.

Open service mode

A traditional bank service outlet can only provide services within five kilometers. In this scope, traditional services have irreplaceable advantages. But when it exceeds this range, the advantages of services provided by the Internet will become more obvious. Therefore, the openness of service modes lies in the fact that banks should not only stick to the existing traditional service modes but also develop Internet channels. It is not limited to serving customers through physical outlets, online banking, and other channels; it can also transfer financial services to mobile clients. To be specific, we can start with three aspects. We can serve customers by building the bank's e-commerce platform, cultivating excellent online customer management teams, and building a more open financial ecosystem.

First, it can build an e-commerce platform for banks, creating a financial and business integration service model. Internet enterprises can do finance, so financial enterprises can also do the Internet, so the banking e-commerce platform came into being. In the Internet financial industry, the mastery of customer information has become a key factor in the success or failure of competition. However, the development of Internet finance, especially the third-party payment modes, has replaced the role of banks as media and reduced the direct contact between banks and customers. The bank can only get information about a certain payment, but it cannot get specific customer information and really understand and analyze the customer's habits and needs. Therefore, in order to reestablish contact with customers, banks can try to bypass the Internet platform intermediary, build an open e-commerce service platform, introduce customer flow, and help banks mine and accumulate customer information.

Second, we can build a more open financial ecosystem. In the process of gradual integration of the Internet and finance, banks should strengthen cooperation, blur the boundaries between different banks, and jointly develop products and services. Banks can cooperate with financial service providers such as funds, securities, small loans, or other banks to form financial alliances or more open platforms in building a harmonious financial ecosystem. For example, some institutions are good at making products, while some are good at selling them. Each partner plays a role in their own fields and provides services to customers. In the process of cooperation, each partner can share data and equipment, and each company can find its own link and do better and deeper. Cooperation is not only limited to the technical level but also goes deeper into the core and concept level of the enterprise so as to truly display the value of the entire chain.

For example, Industrial Bank's interbank platform "Treasurer Qianda" and personal financial platform "Treasurer Wallet" can integrate the financial business of cooperative banks, integrate the service content and service advantages of each bank, facilitate the account conversion between different banks for customers, and provide all-round, one-stop financial solutions for individuals. Here, customers can choose multi-channel financing methods such as bank financing, fund, trust, and insurance, can experience the services of more than 80 online banks, and can enjoy services such as "shopkeeper's wallet," which is immediate redemption to the account, starting at a penny, which will truly realize borderless payment and settlement.

Third, we can build a team of online customer managers, directly conduct product marketing or relationship maintenance for customers online, show the humanization of traditional counter service to more users through online channels, and combine the advantages of various channels with physical outlets, the Internet, mobile terminals, and other channels to create a comprehensive service model for customers. We should break the inherent thinking system of the development of the traditional financial industry, start from the upper decision-making bodies of commercial banks, and face up to the impact of Internet finance

on commercial banks. It is not so much subversion as the coexistence of challenges and opportunities. Commercial banks need to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the existing business service model according to the development stage and characteristics of the bank. For example, the Agricultural Bank of China announced in the second half of 2018 that it would raise Internet finance to the strategic level of the whole bank and set up the Internet Finance Department to conduct the work related to Internet finance construction. In March 2015, ICBC took the lead in releasing the Internet finance brand "e.ICBC", becoming the first commercial bank in China to release the Internet finance brand. Commercial banks need to realize that only by raising the Internet finance development of the banking industry to a strategic height, defining the development direction, formulating practical development goals, and scientifically and rationally formulating the long-term plan for the development of the bank's Internet finance can they make wise choices to meet the challenges of Internet finance.

Secondly, increase investment in commercial banks to develop Internet finance. As an important direction of financial service innovation for commercial banks, the development of Internet financialization has long-term benefits, and commercial banks can sacrifice short-term gains for future development when necessary. On the one hand, we should increase capital investment to provide adequate financial guarantee for the development of Internet financialization; on the other hand, we will strengthen the assessment of Internet finance-related indicators, increase the supporting incentives to promote the completion of indicators, and gradually complete the full production and strategic layout of Internet finance development for commercial banks.

Thirdly, according to the overall strategic deployment of Internet finance, we should reasonably plan the layout of commercial banks' business institutions. Setting Internet finance as one of the important strategies for the overall development of commercial banks requires commercial banks to make a new position for the distribution and setting of business institutions according to the needs of strategic deployment. This requires not only taking into account various factors such as population size, customer type, business environment, and the development degree of Internet finance, but also clarifying the functional positioning of business institutions and promoting the construction of comprehensive, characteristic, and inclusive outlets as a whole. As a service institution, commercial banks should optimize the layout of business institutions, expand their scale, highlight the construction of comprehensive service capacity, and create a financial supermarket with a brand image. It is necessary to build a small and refined market, highlight core capabilities and distinctive services, and create a distinctive financial flagship store. It is necessary to perform the service functions of financial institutions, highlight the characteristics of customer convenience, and lay out financial convenience stores that adapt to the regional environment.

Organizational Structure

The organizational structure of commercial banks needs to be rebuilt, and efforts should be made to achieve a flat organizational structure and market-oriented development and to pay attention to and improve efficiency. The so-called flat organizational structure refers to breaking the vertical organizational management structure of the company, reducing management levels, and establishing a direct customer-oriented marketing and management model. It is a horizontal track to reduce operating costs and improve service efficiency.

1) Drawing on the advanced experience of international and domestic banking sector structure setting, in the face of the "big tail" problem of commercial banks, we should follow the principle of "refined but not complicated," reduce the duplication of settings between departments, the overall plan that unnecessary departments must be removed and departments with less prominent functions should be merged, and downsize the classification of departments and carry out rational setting of departments.

2) We should scientifically and rationally set up departments among organizations. In view of the problem that the front office marketing and technical support departments are understaffed and the back

office management personnel are too many, we should reform the organizational structure from the concept so that more personnel can be enriched in the front office department to provide better services to customers and more professional talents can join the team building of technical support to create a good system environment for customer service. When setting up departments, we should fully consider the changes in customer service needs, adapt to the direction of market development, and truly achieve customer service as the center.

3) Clarify department divisions and improve service efficiency. The scope of authority and responsibility between departments should be clear. When there is a business intersection, a strict, hierarchical, and efficient operation mechanism should be developed to avoid mutual buck passing and excessive checks and balances that lead to duplication of labor, slow approval and innovation processes, and other low service efficiency situations.

References

- Cao, S. (2013). Thoughts and discussions on commercial banks building an Internet financial service system. *Rural Finance Research*, (5), 54-58.
- Lam, K., Shu, J., & Huang, E. (2015). *Four trends shaping China's retail banking landscape*. McKinsey & Company. <http://www.mckinseychina.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/mckinsey-china-pfs-survey-2014.pdf?5c8e08>
- Li, D. (2014). *A brief analysis of Internet finance and its impact on commercial banks* (Doctoral dissertation, Suzhou University).
- Lin, F. (2018). Research on the development model of commercial banks in the Internet finance era. *Economic Outlook the Bohaisea*, (11), 33-34. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/323959216.pdf>
- Mishkin, F. S. (2018). *The economics of money, banking and financial markets* (12th ed.). Pearson.
- O'Reilly, L. (2015, September 24). *Goldman Sachs: Online advertising is about to be 'fundamentally restructured' by Apple, Google, and Facebook*. Insider. <https://www.businessinsider.com/goldman-sachs-news-ads-on-the-block-report-2015-9>
- Qiu, F. (2013). Analysis of the impact and challenges of Internet finance on commercial banks. *Jilin Financial Research*, (8), 44-50.
- Scott, J. (2019). *Social network analysis: A handbook* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications Ltd.
- Shirky, C. (2009). *Here comes everybody: The power of organizing without organization*. Penguin Books.
- Sun, H. (2013). Emerging business models of Internet finance. *China Credit Card*, (9), 50-54. <https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/periodical/zgxyk-zy201309016>
- Wang, J. (2014). *Research on the impact of internet finance on commercial banks and countermeasures* (Doctoral dissertation, Capital University of Economics and Business).
- Wang, J. (2015). Research on measuring the impact of internet finance on commercial banks' profitability—construction and analysis based on the measurement index system. *Financial Theory and Practice*, 2015, (1), 7-12.
- Wang, S., & Zhang, C.. (2014). Chinese model and financial innovation of Internet financial development. *Changbai Academic Journal*, (1), 80-87.
- Wu, P. (2014). *Research on the response strategies of commercial banks under the background of Internet finance* (Doctoral dissertation, Graduate School of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences).
- Xie, P., & Zou, C. (2012). A study on internet based financial model. *Journal of Financial Research*, (12), 11-22. https://qikan.cqvip.com/Qikan/Article/Detail?id=44217703&from=Qikan_Article_Detail
- Xie, P., Zou, C., & Liu, H. (2015). The fundamental theory of internet finance. *Journal of Financial Research*, 422(8), 1-12. <http://www.jryj.org.cn/CN/abstract/abstract373.shtml>
- Xu, S. (2014). *Research on the influence of Internet finance on traditional finance* (Doctoral dissertation, Suzhou University).

- Yuan, B., Li, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2013). Analysis of the impact and countermeasures of the development of Internet finance on Chinese commercial banks. *Financial Theory and Practice*, (12), 66-70.
- Zhang, X. (2014). Principles of internet financial supervision: exploring a new financial supervision paradigm. *Financial Supervision Research*, (2), 6-17.
- Zhang, X. (2020). The impact of internet finance on China's residents' consumption. In J. Guo, X. Xiao, & J. Liu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2019 3rd international conference on education, economics and management research (ICEEMR 2019)* (pp. 515-521). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.191221.125>
- Zhang, Z. (2013). The current status and development strategies of P2P credit in my country. *Huabei Finance*, (7), 38-40. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1007-4392.2013.07.008>
- Zhu, L. (2014). *Research on the strategies of industrial and commercial bank of China to cope with the challenges of Internet finance* (Doctoral dissertation, Xiamen University).
- Zhuo, Z. (2019). Research on using Six Sigma management to improve bank customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Quality Innovation*, 5(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40887-019-0028-6>